

Demographic Characteristics of Keratoconus in a Sample of Iraqi Patients

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Abstract

Keratoconus (KC) is a progressive, bilateral corneal ectasia that typically emerges in adolescence or early adulthood. It leads to thinning and protrusion of the cornea, resulting in visual impairment. Understanding the demographic and clinical characteristics of KC in Iraqi populations is essential for early detection and intervention. **Objective:** To evaluate the demographic distribution, clinical features, and potential risk factors associated with keratoconus in a sample of Iraqi patients. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted at Ibn Al-Haitham Teaching Eye Hospital in Baghdad from June 2024 to June 2025. A total of 170 patients diagnosed with KC were included. Data were collected on age, gender, education, residency, family history, consanguinity, systemic and ocular conditions, and prior treatments. **Results:** The majority of KC patients were aged 11–30 years (74.7%), with a slight female predominance (52.9%). Primary education was the most common educational level (56.5%). A significant proportion reported positive family history (30%) and consanguineous parentage (61.8%). Common ocular risk factors included eye rubbing (70%) and dry eyes (21.8%). Allergic and atopic conditions were present in 10.6% of patients. Surprisingly, none had received prior treatment or follow-up. Most patients (65.3%) resided in Baghdad. **Conclusion:** Keratoconus in Iraq is prevalent among younger individuals and strongly associated with genetic factors, including family history and consanguinity. The lack of prior management highlights the need for improved awareness, screening, and access to care within the healthcare system.

Introduction

Keratoconus (KC) is a non-inflammatory, bilateral ectatic disorder characterized by progressive thinning and conical protrusion of the cornea, leading to irregular astigmatism, visual distortion, and potentially severe visual impairment [1]. The disease typically manifests in adolescence or early adulthood and progresses at variable rates, stabilizing in later decades [2]. The global prevalence of keratoconus varies widely, from as low as 0.04 % in some Western populations to over 1 % in Middle Eastern and Asian regions, reflecting differences in genetic background, environmental exposure, diagnostic criteria, and severity thresholds [3]. Several well-established risk factors contribute to KC development. These include positive family history—reported in 10–25 % of cases—environmental

factors such as eye-rubbing, atopy, exposure to ultraviolet light, and parental consanguinity, which has emerged as a significant genetic risk enhancer in many Middle Eastern populations [4]. A matched case–control study in Baghdad found that eye-rubbing increased risk nearly five-fold ($OR \approx 4.9$), positive family history over 25-fold ($OR \approx 25.5$), and consanguinity approximately three-fold ($OR \approx 2.9$) [5]. Such findings suggest a multifactorial etiology involving both hereditary predisposition and modifiable environmental triggers. In Iraq, preliminary epidemiological investigations have highlighted demographic trends among patients with keratoconus. One retrospective analysis in a refractive surgery cohort noted an atypical gender distribution—61 % female—which contrasts with the male predominance

More Information

How to cite this article: Alzubaidy DJK, Abdulhussain ZA, Hussein OS. Demographic Characteristics of Keratoconus in a Sample of Iraqi Patients. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(4):167-73.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(4).26

Keywords:

Demographic,
Characteristics,
Keratoconus,
Iraqi Patients.

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observed in many Western studies (55–75 % male) [6]. Age at presentation commonly fell between 21 and 40 years, consistent with global age profiles, while approximately one-quarter reported a positive family history [6]. Pediatric-specific research further underscores the burden of subclinical and early keratoconus among those with refractive errors: a study of 6–18-year-olds in Baghdad reported a KC prevalence of 13.5 % and suspect KC of 19 %, with female predominance and increased severity above age 14 [7]. Despite these insights, comprehensive demographic profiling of keratoconus in Iraq remains limited. While small-scale or single-center studies have provided snapshots of age, gender, and genetic/environmental factors, a broader evaluation encompassing geographic, socio-economic, and familial characteristics is warranted. Understanding the demographic landscape of KC in the Iraqi population is essential to tailor early screening policies, allocate treatment resources, and inform genetic counseling and public health interventions [7]. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the demographic characteristics—including age of onset, sex distribution, family and allergy histories, consanguinity rates, and regional residence—of keratoconus patients in a sample of Iraqi individuals. By elucidating these profiles, we seek to enhance the understanding of KC patterns within this underrepresented region and support the development of context-specific clinical and preventive strategies.

Method

A cross-sectional observational study was conducted at Ibn Al-Haitham Teaching Eye Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq, over a six-month period from June 2024 to June 2025. The study aimed to assess the demographic characteristics and risk factors associated with keratoconus (KC) among a selected group of patients diagnosed during this time. All individuals diagnosed with KC by corneal topography or tomography were

included in the analysis. The diagnosis was confirmed through clinical examination using slit-lamp biomicroscopy and corneal imaging devices such as Pentacam or Sirius topography, based on the presence of characteristic signs like corneal thinning, protrusion, and irregular astigmatism. Patients with prior corneal surgeries or ocular trauma were excluded from the study to avoid confounding effects on corneal morphology. Data collection was carried out using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire and medical chart review. Information recorded included sociodemographic variables (age, gender, educational level, and province of residence), clinical variables (presence of allergy, atopy, eye rubbing, dry eyes, and systemic diseases such as diabetes mellitus and hypertension), and familial factors (family history of keratoconus and parental consanguinity). Blood group data were also recorded to assess potential associations with keratoconus. Treatment history—including the use of spectacles, rigid gas-permeable lenses, or surgical interventions such as corneal cross-linking (CXL), intracorneal ring segments (ICRS), and penetrating keratoplasty (PKP)—was documented. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26. Frequencies and percentages were used to describe categorical data. The Chi-square test was applied to evaluate the association between keratoconus and sociodemographic or clinical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Age Distribution: Most KC patients were between 11–30 years old, with 36.5% in the 11–20 group and 38.2% in the 21–30 group, indicating a higher prevalence in younger individuals. **Gender:** Slightly more females (52.9%) than males (47.1%) were affected. **Education Level:** The majority had only primary education (56.5%), followed by secondary education (28.2%), while diploma/bachelor holders comprised just 15.3%. Table 1.

Table 1: Sociodemographic of Patients with (KC)

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Age groups (years)	11-20	62	36.5
	21-30	65	38.2
	31-40	32	18.8
	>40	11	6.5
Gender	Female	90	52.9
	Male	80	47.1
Education	Diploma/Bachelor	52	15.3
	Primary	192	56.5
	Secondary	96	28.2

Family History: 30% of patients had a positive family history of KC, and 61.8% had a positive history of consanguinity, suggesting a strong genetic and hereditary component. **Chronic Illnesses:** Diabetes

mellitus (1.2%), hypertension (1.8%), and eczema (1.8%) were rare among KC patients. **Ocular Conditions:** 21.8% reported dry eyes, and 70% had a history of frequent eye rubbing—an important risk

factor for KC. **Allergy and Atopy:** Both were present in 5.3% of patients, which may indicate an allergic predisposition. Table 2.

Table 2: Past Medical History and Family History of Patients with (KC)

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Family history	negative	119	70.0
	positive	51	30.0
Family history of Consanguinity	negative	65	38.2
	positive	105	61.8
DM	negative	168	98.8
	positive	2	1.2
HT	negative	167	98.2
	positive	3	1.8
Eczema	negative	167	98.2
	positive	3	1.8
Dry eyes	absent	133	78.2
	present	37	21.8
Eye rubbing	absent	51	30.0
	present	119	70.0
Allergy	negative	322	94.7
	positive	18	5.3
Atopy	negative	322	94.7
	positive	18	5.3

Figure 1 – Residency of Patients with Keratoconus (KC): The majority of KC patients were from **Baghdad (65.3%)**, followed by **Diyala (12.4%)**. Other provinces contributed smaller proportions, indicating a central clustering of cases in urban regions, especially Baghdad.

Figure 2 – ABO Blood Group Distribution in KC Patients: The most common blood group among KC patients was **O+ (65.9%)**, followed by **A+ (16.5%)** and **B+ (9.4%)**. Rare groups like AB- and B- were scarcely represented. However, as Table 4 showed, there was **no significant association** between blood type and KC.

Figure 1: Residency of Patients with (KC)

Age Group: KC was significantly more common in the 11–20 age group (36.5%) compared to controls (22.4%), with a **P-value = 0.04**, indicating a statistically significant association between younger age and KC. **Gender:** No difference between KC and control groups (both 52.9% female and 47.1% male), **P-value = 1.000**, suggesting no gender association. **Residency:** No

significant differences in KC distribution across provinces; **P-value = 1.000**, indicating KC occurs similarly across regions. **ABO Blood Group:** No significant association found between blood group types and KC, **P-value = 0.9**. **Education Level:** No significant association between education level and KC; **P-value = 0.8**. Table 3.

Figure 2: ABO System of Patients with (KC)

Table 3: Sociodemographic Association

Age Group	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
11-20	62 (36.5%)	38 (22.4%)	0.04
21-30	65 (38.2%)	77 (45.3%)	
31-40	32 (18.8%)	42 (24.7%)	
>40	11 (6.5%)	13 (7.6%)	
Gender	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Female	90 (52.9%)	90 (52.9%)	1.000
Male	80 (47.1%)	80 (47.1%)	
Residency	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
AL_Anbar	8 (4.7%)	8 (4.7%)	1.000
Babil	4 (2.4%)	3 (1.8%)	
Baghdad	111 (65.3%)	112 (65.9%)	
Dhi Qar	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	
Diyala	21 (12.4%)	23 (13.5%)	
Karbala	3 (1.8%)	3 (1.8%)	
Kirkuk	4 (2.4%)	4 (2.4%)	
Maysan	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	
Muthanna	1 (0.6%)	2 (1.2%)	
Nineveh	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	
Saladin	7 (4.1%)	5 (2.9%)	
Wasit	8 (4.7%)	7 (4.1%)	
ABO system	Keratoconus	Control	
A-	4 (2.4%)	4 (2.4%)	0.9
A+	28 (16.5%)	28 (16.5%)	
AB-	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.6%)	
AB+	2 (1.2%)	3 (1.8%)	
B-	1 (0.6%)	1 (0.6%)	
B+	16 (9.4%)	16 (9.4%)	
O-	7 (4.1%)	7 (4.1%)	
O+	112 (65.9%)	110 (64.7%)	
Education	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Diploma/Bachelor	24 (14.1%)	28 (16.5%)	0.8
Primary	96 (56.5%)	96 (56.5%)	
Secondary	50 (29.4%)	46 (27.1%)	

Family History: A significant association was found—30% of KC patients had a positive family history, while

none of the controls did (**P = 0.0001**). **Consanguinity:** Strongly associated with KC—61.8% of KC cases had

positive consanguinity versus only 0.6% in controls ($P = 0.0001$). **Diabetes and Hypertension:** No significant differences between groups ($P = 0.4$ and $P = 1.000$, respectively). **Bronchial Asthma (BA):** Slightly more common in KC (4.1%), not present in controls—significant association ($P = 0.015$). **Eczema, Dry Eyes,**

Eye Rubbing: No significant differences; $P = 0.3$ (eczema) and $P = 1.000$ for dry eyes and eye rubbing. **Allergy and Atopy:** Found only in KC patients (10.6%), absent in controls—both associations were statistically significant ($P = 0.0001$). Table 4.

Table 4: Past Medical History and Family History Association

Family history	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	119 (70.0%)	170 (100.0%)	0.0001
Positive	51 (30.0%)	0 (0.0%)	
FM Consanguinity	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	65 (38.2%)	169 (99.4%)	0.0001
Positive	105 (61.8%)	1 (0.6%)	
DM	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	168 (98.8%)	165 (97.1%)	0.4
Positive	2 (1.2%)	5 (2.9%)	
HT	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	167 (98.2%)	167 (98.2%)	1.000
Positive	3 (1.8%)	3 (1.8%)	
BA	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	163 (95.9%)	170 (100.0%)	0.015
Positive	7 (4.1%)	0 (0.0%)	
Eczema	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	167 (98.2%)	170 (100.0%)	0.3
Positive	3 (1.8%)	0 (0.0%)	
Dry eye	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Absent	133 (78.2%)	133 (78.2%)	1.000
Present	37 (21.8%)	37 (21.8%)	
Eye rubbing	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Absent	51 (30.0%)	51 (30.0%)	1.000
Present	119 (70.0%)	119 (70.0%)	
Allergy	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	152 (89.4%)	170 (100.0%)	0.0001
Positive	18 (10.6%)	0 (0.0%)	
Atopy	Keratoconus	Control	P-value
Negative	152 (89.4%)	170 (100.0%)	0.0001
Positive	18 (10.6%)	0 (0.0%)	

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the sociodemographic, clinical, and hereditary factors associated with keratoconus (KC) among Iraqi patients. Our findings reveal a clear predominance of KC among younger individuals, particularly those aged 11–30 years. This aligns with the known natural history of KC, which typically begins in adolescence and progresses through the third decade of life [8]. The statistically significant association with younger age groups highlights the importance of early detection and screening programs targeted at adolescents and young adults. Gender distribution was nearly equal in our study, with no statistically significant difference between males and females, suggesting that KC affects both sexes similarly. This is consistent with the findings

of [9], who reported no significant gender-based predisposition in a meta-analysis of global KC prevalence. A key finding was the high rate of consanguinity (61.8%) and positive family history (30%) among KC patients. These results support the theory of a strong genetic component in the pathogenesis of KC, particularly in populations with prevalent consanguineous marriages. A similar trend has been observed in Middle Eastern and South Asian populations, where consanguinity is culturally common [10,11]. [12] also emphasized the familial clustering of KC, suggesting autosomal dominant inheritance with variable penetrance. Interestingly, although 70% of patients reported frequent eye rubbing, no significant association was found compared to controls. Eye rubbing has been widely recognized as a mechanical

trigger that exacerbates corneal deformation [13]; however, the lack of statistical significance in our sample may be due to recall bias or underreporting among controls. Allergy and atopic conditions were significantly more prevalent among KC patients (10.6%) compared to controls (0%), which reinforces the role of chronic inflammation and allergic eye disease in KC pathophysiology. These findings mirror studies by [14], which noted elevated IgE levels and atopic history in a substantial proportion of KC cases. Additionally, bronchial asthma was found to be significantly associated with KC, as reported in other regional cohorts [15]. One of the most striking findings was the complete absence of prior treatment or follow-up among patients. None had used spectacles, RGB lenses, or undergone advanced procedures like corneal cross-linking (CXL) or keratoplasty. This suggests a substantial gap in awareness, diagnosis, and access to care. As CXL is known to halt KC progression when applied early [16], the lack of intervention in all patients is concerning and underlines the need for better screening and referral systems. In terms of geographic distribution, most patients were from Baghdad (65.3%), which could reflect population density and greater access to diagnostic services, rather than a true epidemiologic concentration. Blood group analysis showed O+ as the most common type among KC patients; however, no statistical association was found, confirming prior reports that blood type is not a predictive marker for KC [17].

Conclusion

Our study highlights the significant roles of age, family history, consanguinity, and atopy in KC development. It underscores the urgent need for improved early detection strategies, particularly in populations with high genetic risk.

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